

A Study to Know the Impact of AI in Influencing Consumer to Buy Branded Products

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Abstract:- This research article aims to investigate how AI affects consumer's decision-making process when making purchases of branded products. Artificial Intelligence technologies are becoming more and more widespread throughout society because they are the backbone for innovative value propositions and distinctive client experiences. Better customer experiences strengthen the relationship between consumers and brand and help brands different from its competitors. Companies must employ artificial intelligence to safeguard the consumers' data in order to win over consumer confidence. The connection between AI marketing activities and brand preferences was also influenced through brand experience. The development of artificial intelligence has increased customer happiness even more, making it even more crucial in the contemporary environment. Insights into consumer behaviour patterns enable companies create more individualised customer experiences, which increases the likelihood that customers will switch their loyalties to that specific brand. Artificial intelligence (AI)-enabled technology was used by e-commerce businesses to ascertain client demands and preferences for online products and services. The artificial intelligence maintains a record of the customer's preferences, buying habits, frequency of purchases, and average purchase price during a certain time period. Marketers could use artificial intelligence (AI) to determine the marketing tactics that generated the most interest from consumers. Based on this data, businesses may create a flawless strategy for future advertising that will probably result in more sales. It enables Ecommerce Businesses comprehensive client information. Without requiring human participation, AI can be implemented to track complaints from customers and inquiries. AI could assist you in decision-making about sales, website visitor behaviour analysis, customer behaviour prediction, and company strategy optimization. This study employee convenient sampling method. Targeted groups were between the age of 18 years to 44 years. This study reported that the influence of AI in buying behaviour of consumer and concluded with factors.

Keywords:- Artificial Intelligence, consumers, branded products, industry.

I. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the use of artificial intelligence (AI) has spread to various industries such as marketing and sales. AI is being used today to analyse vast amounts of data and gain insights into customer behaviour. This allows companies to personalize their marketing messages, recommend better products, and improve the overall

customer experience. As the marketplace becomes more competitive, companies are looking for ways to differentiate themselves and persuade consumers to buy their products.

AI can train machines to recognize patterns in large amounts of data using technologies such as natural language processing, genetic algorithms, and deep learning. AI includes systems that think rationally and resemble humans. AI can be clearly defined as technology capable of performing tasks that require intelligence when performed by humans. The introduction of AI into various marketing processes opens up many opportunities for marketers and increases practitioners' interest in its various applications. Marketing scientists are therefore conducting more and more research in this area.

The purpose of this study is to examine the impact of AI on consumer behaviour when purchasing branded products. The use of artificial intelligence (AI) has increased significantly in recent years. Companies across multiple industries are integrating AI into their operations, and marketing is no exception.

Consumer shopper behaviour refers to the actions and choices consumers make when purchasing products and services. AI is having a profound impact on consumer shopper behaviour by enabling businesses to provide personalized experiences and recommendations based on consumer preferences. By analysing large amounts of data, AI can identify patterns of consumer behaviour and preferences, which can be used to create targeted marketing campaigns and personalized experiences.

AI has transformed the way marketers interact with consumers and has had a profound impact on how consumers shop from brands. With the help of AI, businesses can analyse large amounts of data and gain insights into consumer behaviour and preferences. You can use this knowledge to create personalized experiences and improve customer retention.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A recent development in the fields of science, medicine, education, business, and the car industry are artificial intelligence. It has now impacted marketing as well (Jarek and Mazurek, 2019). Research and marketing have intriguing new potential thanks to AI's rapid progress (Mustak et. al, 2021).

- Image recognition, speech recognition, decision-making, and language translation are just a few examples of how computers can think, and act more effectively than humans can (CXPA, 2018). According to Sterne (2017), AI is capable of doing the "three Ds": detect, determine,

and develop. The capacity of AI to recognise the most common and anticipated traits of a topic matter is known as detection. AI may decide which qualities should be valued and which should be disregarded. The term "decide" describes an AI's capacity to make a choice after carefully weighing a large number of factors and selecting the most significant one.

The contact between customers and brands will alter as a result of speech recognition, which relies on basic neural network software. The speech recognition technology is incorporated and can interpret what the customer is saying (Dash, 2015). For instance, when Alexa, an e-commerce speech AI, was put into the Amazon Echo, it allowed customers to make purchases by speaking to the device. This allowed Amazon to capture 70% of the market for smart speakers (Avinaash, 2018).

- AI is a major factor in both B2C and B2B marketing. According to a study by KRC Research, artificial intelligence (AI) has a bigger influence on marketing than social media and will support firms in personalising interactions with customers through Chabot. Also, 79% of the 717 marketers questioned in the Forrester research by Emarsys believed AI made workflow more strategic than it was (Avinaash, 2018). According to Jarek & Mazurek (2019), marketing activities are significantly influenced by AI. The retail industry, which is characterised by regular client contact and generates a significant quantity of data regarding consumer traits and transactions, is where AI's effects are most apparent.

Consumers benefited from a wide range of benefits thanks to AI, including more efficient operations like automated payments, higher-quality search engines, and round-the-clock customer support. Via automated product recommendations, relevant product suggestions, personalised customer care, and post-purchase support, AI offers the consumer a novel experience. Besides from enhancing the consumer-brand interaction, AI also allows customers the option to digitally test products. The majority of customers do believe that AI will improve life by addressing complicated issues, but others fear that it will eliminate their employment (PwC, 2017).

- In order to get, acquire, and discard items and services that satiate their needs and desires, consumers engage in a process of physical activity and decision-making known as the consumer buy behaviour process. Future behaviour may be predicted with the use of such a process' analysis (Qazzafi, 2019). The consumer purchase decision-making process consists of five phases: need identification, information search, alternative evaluation, purchase choice, and post-purchase behaviour. These stages correspond to the stages that consumers go through on their travels before opting to own a product. The customer can bypass one or more steps. Depending on what they perceive (Kotler et al., 2017).

Since it involves the human mind, consumer buy behaviour is difficult to understand. Nevertheless, in the setting of a digital platform, it is feasible thanks to AI, which may assist in evaluating and forecasting consumer purchase behaviour. Customers express their requirements, wants, and views on the digital platform using a variety of channels, including online, mobile, and face-to-face discussions as well as search, comments, blogs, Tweets, likes, and videos (Court, et al., 2009). Hence, the amount, speed, diversity, and accuracy of the provision of consumer data is constantly increasing. AI can play a part in transforming such a data flood into valuable customer intelligence (Kietzmann, 2018).

- Consumer purchasing is the act of choosing choices to satisfy all demands (Jalal, 2020, Qazzafi, 2019). The five processes of consumer purchase decision-making include need identification, information seeking, weighing options, choosing a course of action, and post-purchase behaviour (Kotler, 2017). One of the most popular uses of AI is for identifying customer preferences (Muthuveloo & Ping, 2014). Consumer data continues to increase in volume, variety, speed, and accuracy. AI assists in converting this data flood into valuable customer insights (Kietzmann, Paschen, and Treen, 2018). Marketers base their decisions on consumer purchasing trends when deciding on their marketing strategies and predicting sales. AI uses this information to make suggestions for product display and cataloguing to merchants (Avinash and Jayan, 2018). Recognizing a need is the first step in the consumer journey. Businesses should assess what consumers need and develop marketing tactics that may meet those demands (Kotler et al., 2017). The requirements of an individual determine categorizations, not brands (Batra and Keller, 2016). Hence, it is difficult to keep track of someone's requirements and goals.
- When customers communicate their requirements and wants online, AI can analyze those needs and wants. AI will assist marketers in creating more thorough customer profiles more quickly and in real-time. Consumers' online behaviours, including social media status updates, online purchases, comments, and postings, create their digital footprints, which machine learning then uses to automatically update the profiles of customers. For instance, Microsoft's AI system Azure assisted the media company Astr in developing customer profiles by analysing billions of data points, determining consumers' wants in seconds, and then personalising online content to fit consumers' preferences. Moreover, AI supports the detection of customer demands and wants. For instance, Pinterest employs picture recognition to identify the specific fashion tastes of users based on the photographs they pin to the platform, and then the platform shows the users the images that are applicable to them (Kietzmann, 2018). Also, the AI-powered Adobe Audience Manager's customized modelling assisted in identifying potential customers with comparable characteristics and interests to the present users (Michael, 2010).

- According to Pornpimon Kachamas, Sukree Sinthupinyo, and Achara Chandrachi's research from 2019, the goal of this study is to create an analytical tool that can help online vendors forecast customer behaviour based on Dentsu AISAS perspectives. The author also noted that the study can gather information from online paggers about customers. consumed items All of their real research is restricted to non-consumable products. Laith T. Khrais (2020) studied how key technology advancements in e-commerce are intended to sway consumer behaviour in favour of particular goods and companies.
 - Shyna K and Vishal M (2017) Studied "Artificial Intelligence in E-Commerce" In his article, the author discusses the role of artificial intelligence thinking in online business and how it is used in many fields of online commerce. The ability of computerised thinking to gather and analyse massive amounts of data and provide options for action is astounding. This invention is now being used in web-based company to identify designs based on browsing, purchase history, credit checks, account information, and so forth. The basis for creating customised suggestions for each consumer is built on the data acquired at that time. Microsoft and Google are now investing in new AI initiatives. To better understand their customers and provide a better customer experience, some online business groups have begun developing various types of AI.
 - Girish Punj (2012) studied "Consumer Decision Making on the Web: A Theoretical Analysis and Research Guidelines". According to the author's research, people may choose higher-quality options while purchasing online. In any event, whether or not most customers are aware of this possibility is a contentious matter.
- Therefore, the purpose of this investigation is to determine how specific aspects of electronic environments favourably influence consumers' abilities to make better decisions and identify data preparation techniques that would enable customers to make better quality decisions while shopping online. To identify elements that may have an influence on choice quality in electronic settings, a cross-disciplinary hypothetical investigation based on components pulled from financial aspects (e.g., time expenditures), figuring (e.g., proposition operators), and brain science (e.g., choice approaches) is used. The investigation is crucial from a hypothetical standpoint since it examines a substantial portion of the dynamics of online purchasers, namely the impact of the electronic environment on the purchasing power of consumers.
- Girish Punj (2012) studied ways by which AI will influence Consumer Behaviour. Associations and sponsors will benefit from understanding all the data and realising how AI is affecting customers in order to stay prepared. The more you think about your consumers and how they behave, the more you may adjust your operations and marketing strategies to better meet their needs.
- ✓ **Customers' use of search engines:** Normal websites will significantly change how people shop and what they buy. Using these sites, we observe that the typical expenditure of a customer for each encounter is significantly rising. Typical locations direct customers through a far more intelligent route, allowing them to make purchases before customer fatigue sets in or the customer becomes distracted.
 - ✓ **Client Engagement:** According to studies, if AI was present, 49% of users would return to an online space. The client is paired with suitable hosts and posts as well as experiences and surroundings that will enhance their stay. With such help, the customer is less likely to shop someplace else the next time they need a break.
 - ✓ **Customer convenience:** The possible outcomes that AI is opening up are vast, and they will significantly improve the buyer's buying experience. This suggests that businesses should keep an eye out for trends.
 - ✓ **Customer Trust in Brands:** By providing a tremendous amount of substantial value as a result of their customers' preferences, marketers may build trust with consumers in the simplest way possible. This is when AI comes into play. Customers trust AI-driven products that personalise the experience while providing a large amount of value, as we have seen with any resemblance of Google Now.
 - The increased use of social media by businesses and consumers suggests interesting data sources to understand consumer behaviour (Qiu et al., 2015; Zhang et al., 2016). Social media information informs corporate planning and fosters business optimization (Luo & Zhang, 2013). In order to build brand equity, research looks at the effects of user-generated content on Twitter followers' perceptions of brands and product sales (Kuksov et al., 2013). In order to provide information or material for brand perceptions, further research also examines the social structures of the brands on social media (Culotta & Cutler, 2016). The advantages of social media analytics assist in understanding the volume, scope, and ambiguity of data sources, which poses obstacles. This contributes to the efficient algorithmic decision-making framework. More examination on the relationship between social networking websites and brand equity across all social media is encouraged by recent studies. Moreover, a theory of brand equity has been developed around the dynamics of social media and brand equity (Aaker, 1991; Keller, 1993).
 - The stimulus-organism-response (SOR) model was chosen as the study's main conceptual framework. The SOR model describes how environmental cues affect people's internal states, behavioural reactions, and the course of events by elaborating on the relationships between inputs (stimulus), processes (organism), and outputs (response). It has been frequently utilised to comprehend customer behaviour in marketing literature (Fan et al. 2022). Most crucially, the SOR model can accurately forecast how users would react to novel technology. Kim et al. (2020) used the SOR model to analyse customer behaviour in the real world and how they reacted to virtual reality travel experiences. The SOR framework has been used by several academics to

- comprehend customers' online behaviour (Islam et al. 2020; Zhu et al. 2019). Wu et al. (2021), using the SOR paradigm as a guide, examined how ambient cues from travel applications affected visitors' emotional and behavioural reactions. The SOR model was used in this study to describe how artificial intelligence (AI) influences brand experience (organism), which in turn influences brand preference and repurchase intention (response).
- AI marketing initiatives may influence how consumers react and decide (Chen et al. 2022; Libai et al. 2020). By client orientation, information sharing, and addressing customer problems, bank staff improve consumer trust through interactions with customers (Roberts-Lombard and Petzer 2021). Such marketing initiatives are crucial for banks since they have to share financial data or updates in order to offer expert, specialised services. By making it simple for clients to get information about products or services, AI can decrease their physical and temporal distance from banks (Chung et al. 2020). Nevertheless, they solely focused on chatbots. Chung et al. (2020) and Cheng and Jiang (2021) were pioneers in evaluating the impact of AI marketing initiatives on consumer behaviours and customer-firm interactions. The goal of this study was to present an up-to-date account of AI applications in Hong Kong's banking sector in order to further the conversation on AI marketing initiatives and its components. AI marketing initiatives comprise five aspects, according to Cheng and Jiang (2021): interaction, information, accessibility, customisation, and entertainment. The context of banking does not apply to entertainment. Banking consumers tend to be more transactional (or utilitarian) oriented than those in other commercial situations (Rodrigues et al. 2016). People seldom view financial transactions or activities as joyful or entertaining, hence only the other four aspects were used in this study. Customers and the brand's AI bots interact by exchanging messages. When clients connect with or converse with AI agents, social interaction is a crucial aspect of the customer experience (Godey et al. 2016).
 - Interactions with people, things, processes, and surroundings all contribute to brand experience and cause cognitive, emotional, sensory, and behavioural reactions (Trivedi 2019). A multidimensional term, brand experience may be quantified in four different ways: sensory, emotive, behavioural, and intellectual (Brakus et al. 2009). The customer-brand connection is impacted by AI marketing initiatives (Nguyen et al. 2021). Customers are more likely to be happy with AI services when the quality of the AI is excellent. According to Trivedi (2019), if AI can give consumers fast, accurate, and relevant information, they will continue to utilise the technology as a result of the positive experience. According to Cheng and Jiang (2021), AI activities had a direct impact on chatbot communication quality, which had a good impact on the customer-brand connection and led to favourable consumer reactions. According to Hwang et al. (2021), service robots delivered functional and emotional value effectively in the setting of hospitality and tourism, which boosted customer satisfaction. Customers reported higher levels of pleasure when they thought a purchase activity was fun, according to Kim et al. (2021)
 - As identifying consumer brand preference is a crucial first step in understanding consumer brand choice, marketers have long paid close attention to it. Horsky et al (2006) example highlights the value of include brand preference information. In the model of brand preference. Brand preferences are the propensities of consumers to favour a specific brand (Overby and Lee, 2006). According to Hellier et al. (2003) and Zajonc and Markus (1980), it refers to the behavioural patterns that show how much customers like one brand over another. When it comes to accurately expressing customer perceptions of brands, brand preference is near to reality. In the marketplace, buyers frequently have to choose between a variety of possibilities (Dhar, 1999). The brand strength is shown in the bias customers hold for a particular brand as a result of comparing it to alternatives (Biel, 1992).
- As a result, modifications in consumer brand preferences have an impact on brand performance. market shares, too (Sriram et al., 2006). Moreover, brand preference mixes the desired traits and customer perceptions; as a result, it provides a subtle and indirect method of evaluating important attributes (Keller, 1993; O'Connor and Sullivan, 1995; Schoenfelder and Harris, 2004). In order to create a successful brand strategy, brand positioning, and to provide insights for product development, it is thus thought that identifying customer brand preferences is essential (Alamro and Rowley, 2011; Alamro, 2010; Horsky et al., 2006). Understanding brand preferences helps create powerful brands that can create lasting relationships with customers.
- The importance of brand creation by businesses, enterprises, and many other organisations is emphasised by Fournier, S. M. (1996). The authors present a model that illustrates the interaction between brands and customers. This paradigm views brands and customers as a team or partners with a focus on interpersonal interactions and a two-way relationship. According to Park, C. W., Jaworski, B. J., and MacInnis (1986), the core activity of marketing is communicating a brand's image to a target market of consumers. A framework for managing brands has been presented by the author and is known as "brand concept management (BCM)." The actions are to pick, introduce, elucidate, and strengthen the idea of a brand. If the brand concept is experiential, symbolic, or utilitarian affects how this concept-image tie is maintained. The market performance of the brand should be greatly improved by maintaining this relationship. This framework is a step-by-step approach with a variety of activities. Thus, this framework provides a suitable technique for managing brands' reputations.
 - J. N. Kapferer (2017), Luxury brands are those that are extremely coveted and associated with rich people. They are not fundamental requirements or desires, but rather the opulent demands of society's upper crust. According to the author, there is a certain ambiguity around premium brands and notions. The study focuses on the

distinctions between a luxury brand and a regular brand. According to current definitions of luxury brands as well as luxury definition, the disparities have evaporated. Nonetheless, the article shows that there are relatively substantial disparities in the administration of luxury brands and management of ordinary or quality companies.

III. OBJECTIVES

- To identify the different ways that AI is being used to influence consumer purchase intention for branded products.
- To understand the impact of AI on consumer decision-making processes.

IV. RESEARCH GAP

In spite of the developing body of writing on the effect of AI on buyer behaviour, there's a need of inquire about that particular centre on the impact of AI on buyer behaviour when it comes to buying branded items. Whereas a few thinks about have examined the effect of AI on buyer decision-making and buy behaviour more broadly, few have inspected the part of AI in forming consumers' states of mind and discernments toward branded items, or how it influences their purchasing patterns. Subsequently, there's a require for encourage inquire about that investigates the particular ways in which AI is affecting consumers' choices to purchase branded items, and how companies can use this innovation to way better get it and lock in with their clients.

V. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

- To conduct the survey, a questionnaire was created.
- To get responses from the sample and gather primary data, the questionnaire was made available as a google form.
- Analyses of the submitted replies.
- Conclusions were drawn based on the respondents' responses rather than just the results of the questionnaire.

The created questionnaire was split into two sections. Personal questions were asked in the first section to help determine the participants' demographics. The second section included inquiries on the study. The questionnaire was designed such that any participant could find the questions to be pertinent and had no trouble comprehending them. The key topics covered in the questionnaire were AI's role in encouraging consumers to purchase branded goods. Despite being short and to the point, this survey form nearly precisely gathered all the data needed to understand how AI influences customer purchases of branded goods.

VI. RESEARCH DESIGN

The methods and processes used to carry out a study are referred to as the research design. It enables researchers to focus in on the research techniques that are best suitable for the field and frame the study accordingly. Most of the time, an effective study design minimises data bias and fosters more confidence in the veracity of the information gathered. It is basically divided into two different categories as follows:

Fig. 1: Research Design

"Research that is conducted when the problem is not clearly defined is referred to as exploratory research." When conducting research on a subject that hasn't been extensively studied previously, descriptive research is the best option. When collecting quantitative data and applying various statistical methods for analysis, it is applied.

"The purpose of descriptive research is to describe the characteristics of a population or a phenomenon."

We did descriptive research to learn more about people's investment habits and preferences. By gathering and analysing primary data in the form of a survey through a questionnaire and secondary data in the form of a literature study, we were able to meet our needs and better understand

the consumer perspective towards various investment sectors.

VII. SOURCE OF DATA

- **Primary data:** This refers to information that has been gathered directly from sources using various methods, such as interviews, questionnaires, etc. Primary data for this study was gathered through the use of questionnaires.
- **Secondary Data:** Secondary data refers to the data existing in the pre-existing domain i.e., it refers to the data which have already been collected and analysed by someone else. The secondary data involved in this project has been gathered from the internet.

Fig. 2: Source of Data

VIII. TOOLS OF DATA COLLECTION

In this study, only Google Forms were used to gather the data.

IX. SAMPLE DESIGN

- **Duration of Study:** this study is conducted over a period of 30 days.
- **Sample Size:** The sample size for this study was 100 people.
- **Sampling Methods:** Simple random sampling was utilised in the study to ensure that every participant had an equal chance of being chosen as a sample.

- **Area or Location of Sample Work:** The sampling will be place throughout India.

X. METHOD & TECHNIQUE OF DATA ANALYSIS

The data analysis process, also known as the data analysis phases, involves gathering all the information, processing it, evaluating the data, and applying it to find patterns and other insights. The following are the steps involved in data analysis:

Fig. 3: Method & Technique Of Data Analysis

- **Data Gathering:** You may determine the sort of data you want to use, the purpose of your study, and the data you want to evaluate by asking yourself these questions.
- **Data Collection:** The information has to be gathered from your sources according to your specified needs. Direct observation, focus groups, interviews, surveys, questionnaires, case studies, and other types of sources

- are a few examples. Be sure to prepare the data for analysis before gathering it.
- **Data Analysis:** Utilising software and other tools to help you assess, interpret, and make conclusions from the data is known as data analysis. Examples of data analysis tools include Excel, Python, R, Looker, Rapid Miner, Chartio, Metabase, Redash, and Microsoft Power BI.

- **Data Interpretation:** It's time to examine your results and choose the best course of action in light of your findings now that you have your results.
- **Data Visualisation:** It means "graphically show your information in a way that people can read and understand it" in technical terms. There are several possibilities available to you, including graphs, maps, charts, bullet points, and more. Visualisation assists in making significant discoveries by letting you compare datasets and see correlations.

XI. DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Data analysis is the process of looking at data using various statistical techniques in order to obtain relevant information. Since the data analysis information will be needed to comprehend the findings and conclusions, this section of the study report is vital. The conclusions and findings must satisfy the research objectives of the study.

Data analysis is done based on the study elements that are considered in relation to the research objectives. Among the research variables in the current study are the demographic parameters, investor preferences, income from investments, and decision-making about risk and return. Identifying whether the outcomes are anticipated or unanticipated is the aim.

A. Part 1

Table 1: Age

AGE	Counts	Percentage
18-24	75	75%
25-34	17	17%
35-44	8	8%

Chart 1: Age

Primary research is conducted among the people who are in the age 18 years to 44 years. Furthermore, people are divided into three group of age in accordance with changing preference after certain age.

100 participants from 18 to 44 years had participated in the research. Among those people 75% are from 18-24 years age group, 17% are from 25-34 years age group and 8% are from 35-44 age group.

Table 2: Gender

Gender	Counts	Percentage
Male	43	43%
Female	57	57%

Chart 2: Gender

The information shown illustrates the gender distribution within a certain population or group. There are 57 people who have been classified as female and 43 people

who have been classified as male. Females (57%) appear to make up a larger portion of the group than men (43%).

Table 3: Occupation

Occupation	Counts	Percentage
Employed	17	17%
Self-employed	7	7%
Student	74	74%
Housewife	2	2%

Chart 3: Occupation

The data illustrates how people are distributed throughout various professions. Individuals are divided into four occupational groups based on the above figure: employed, self-employed, students, and housewives. A considerable 74% of the club's participants are students, making up the major portion of the group. At 17%, employed

people represent a somewhat lower percentage. 7% of the population is made up of independent contractors. At 2%, housewives make up the smallest category. According to the statistics, the category appears to be mostly made up of students, with substantially lesser proportions of working, self-employed, and housewives.

B. Part 2

Table 4: Are you familiar with the concept of Artificial Intelligence (AI)?

Familiar with AI	Counts	Percentage
Yes	95	95%
May Be	5	5%

Chart 4: Familiar with AI

The data presents to how well-versed a group of people is on the idea of artificial intelligence (AI). There are two possibilities available for respondents in the data: "Yes" and "May Be" (which denotes ambiguity or a passing acquaintance). The percentage column demonstrates the percentage of respondents in each category of familiarity in relation to the overall percentage of respondents. 95% of

respondents indicated that they were familiar with AI by selecting "Yes." The remaining 5% of respondents responded, "May Be," indicating that they are unsure or just somewhat familiar with AI. According to the findings, a sizable portion of respondents are familiar with the idea of artificial intelligence, whereas a far smaller proportion showed confusion or merely partial insight.

Table 5: How frequently do you use chatbots, virtual assistants, and other AI-powered technology in your day-to-day activities?

Frequent use of AI Technology	Counts	Percentage
Very often	21	21%
Often	43	43%
Occasionally	29	29%
Rarely	4	4%
Never	3	3%

Chart 5: Frequent use of AI Technology

The above figure given has associated with how frequently people use chatbots, virtual assistants, and other AI-powered technologies in their regular lives. Regarding how often people utilise AI-powered technology in their regular activities, the data offers five response options: "Very frequently," "often," "often," "occasionally," "rarely," and "never."

In the percentage column, it is shown what percentage of responses fall into each frequency group overall. Among respondents, 21% say they utilise AI technology "Very often. According to 43% of respondents, AI technology is used "often." 29% of respondents said they "occasionally"

utilise AI technology. 4% of respondents said they "Rarely" employ AI technology. 3% of those surveyed said they "Never" utilise AI technology.

A sizable proportion of respondents (64%) said they use AI technology "Very often" or "Often" in their daily lives, indicating that this group uses AI relatively often. According to the survey, 29% of respondents said they use AI technology "occasionally," which means they use it less regularly but still utilise it in their daily activities. Only 7% of respondents said they used AI technology "Rarely" or "Never," indicating that it has little to no impact on their day-to-day activities.

Table 6: Do you prefer branded goods over generic ones when shopping?

Generic Ones/ Branded Ones Shopping	Counts	Percentage
Very often	19	19%
Often	35	35%
Occasionally	37	37%
Rarely	9	9%

Chart 6: Generic Ones/ Branded Ones Shopping

The demographic data given refers to people's preferences when it comes to purchasing for products, especially if they like branded versus generic items. Regarding how frequently people choose to purchase branded items versus generic ones when shopping, the data offers four response options: "Very frequently," "often," "occasionally," and "rarely."

Each preference category's percentage of respondents, as compared to all respondents, is shown in the percentage column. 19% of those polled said they "Very often" choose branded items. Branded items are preferred "often" by 35% of respondents. 37% of those surveyed "Occasionally" like branded items. Branded items are "Rarely" preferred by 9% of respondents.

In every aspect, 71% of respondents choose branded items either "Very often" or "Often" when they shop. This implies that people prioritise branded goods while making purchases. A sizable fraction (an additional 37%) favours branded goods "Occasionally," suggesting that consumers occasionally choose for branded products but also take generic alternatives into consideration. A lower percentage (9%), who choose branded items "Rarely," suggests that people frequently choose generic goods when shopping.

In a nutshell the findings show that most respondents have a preference for branded items, albeit to various degrees, whereas a smaller proportion of respondents tend to choose generic products more frequently when they purchase.

Table 7: Have you seen that suggestions generated by artificial intelligence affect the brands of goods you choose to buy?

AI affect the brands	Counts	Percentage
Frequently	14	14%
Sometimes	75	75%
Not Really	10	10%
Never	1	1%

Chart 7: AI affect the brands

The data displays to how artificial intelligence (AI)-generated suggestions affect the brands of items that people decide to purchase. Addressing the frequency with which AI-generated ideas affect people's brand decisions while making purchases, the data offers four answer options: The following are the possible answers: "Frequently," "Sometimes," "Not Really," and "Never."

According to the total number of responses, the percentage column shows the percentage of respondents in each category of AI impact. When picking brands, 14% of respondents said that AI ideas "Frequently" affect them. 75% of respondents said that AI ideas "Sometimes" affected them. 10% of respondents said that their brand choices are "Not Really" influenced by AI recommendations. Only 1% of respondents said that AI recommendations "Never" influence their brand preferences.

A large percentage of respondents (75%) indicated that AI-generated recommendations "Sometimes" influence their brand selections, indicating that AI has a moderate impact on consumers' purchase decisions. 14 percent of respondents, a lesser but still considerable amount, stated that AI recommendations "Frequently" affect their brand selections, indicating a more significant influence. A small percentage of respondents (10%) indicated that AI recommendations "Not Really" affect their brand preferences, suggesting that AI has only a tiny impact on their purchase decisions. One percent of respondents responded that AI recommendations "Never" influenced their brand decisions, indicating that AI seldom had any impact on this small population.

Table 8: How likely are you to investigate a product that an AI system suggests?

Willing to investigate AI products	Counts	Percentage
Very likely	13	13%
Likely	52	52%
Neutral	29	29%
Unlikely	5	5%
Very unlikely	1	1%

Chart 8: Willing to investigate AI products

According to the figures, and 29% of individuals are impartial and 65% are willing to research a product that an AI system recommends. This shows that there is a widespread degree of confidence in product suggestions driven by AI. However, a sizable proportion of individuals are also either reluctant or extremely unlikely to look into product recommendations made by AI, which shows that some consumers may be worried about the objectivity or bias of these ideas.

Reasons whether consumers could look at proposals for AI products include: They contend that compared to human-curated lists, AI systems may offer suggestions that are more precise and tailored ; they want to test out novel goods and services that they would not have otherwise thought about ; they have faith that AI systems will provide safe and dependable advice.

Reasons whether individuals might be reluctant to research recommendations for AI products include some have reservations about the objectivity or accuracy of AI systems; people are concerned that AI systems may jeopardise their privacy; consumers like to choose the goods and services they want to purchase on their own.

The standing of the business offering the AI suggestions. People are more inclined to believe AI suggestions from businesses they already have confidence in and who have a solid record of accomplishment of delivering accurate and trustworthy information. The degree of openness around how the AI system operates. If people are aware of how the system functions and how the suggestions are created, they are more inclined to trust AI advice customising the AI suggestions. If users have the option to tailor AI suggestions to their own requirements and interests, they are more inclined to believe them.

Table 9: What elements influence your decision to buy a branded product based on AI recommendations? (Select all that apply)

Elements to buy a branded product through AI	Counts	Percentage
Personalized suggestions	46	46%
Positive reviews from other users	86	86%
Relevant product information	47	47%
Discounts or special offers	24	24%
Previous positive experiences with AI recommendations	6	6%

Chart 9: Elements to buy a branded product through AI

The information given refers to the factors that people consider when choosing to purchase a branded product based on AI suggestions. The information provides five components or variables that may affect a person's choice to buy a branded product that an AI recommendation. Selecting every element that applied to them was asked of the respondents.

The percentage column shows the percentage of respondents—relative to the total respondents—who chose each criterion. "Personalised suggestions" have an impact on 46% of responders. 86% of respondents, a sizable majority, said they are influenced by "Positive reviews from other users." 47% of respondents said that "Relevant product information" has an impact on them. "Discounts or special offers" are seen as an influencing factor by 24% of respondents. 6% of respondents said that "Previous positive experiences with AI" affected them.

The majority of respondents (86%) said they take into account "positive reviews from other users" when making a

purchase based on AI suggestions, making it the most important consideration. Getting good reviews from others may have a big effect on purchasing decisions. Both "Relevant Product Information" and "Personalised Suggestions" are significant, with 47% and 46% of respondents, respectively, perceiving these elements to be relevant in their choices. With 24% of respondents giving "discounts or special offers" some thought, they are somewhat influential. With only 6% of respondents identifying it, "Previous positive experiences with AI recommendations" is the least significant reason.

Therefore, the data demonstrates that when people choose to buy branded items based on AI recommendations, favourable user ratings, pertinent product information, and personalised suggestions are the most important aspects. Discounts or special offers also have an impact, albeit less so, and the decision-making process is least affected by prior favourable experiences with AI suggestions.

Table 10: Do you believe artificial intelligence-generated material for branded items, such as reviews, ads, or product descriptions?

Believe in AI generated material for branded items	Counts	Percentage
Completely trust	4	4%
Mostly trust	62	62%
Neutral	28	28%
Somewhat distrust	6	6%
Do not trust at all	0	0

Chart 10: Believe in AI generated material for branded items

All of this data refers to people's opinions of artificial intelligence-generated content for branded goods, such as reviews, advertisements, or product descriptions. Five choices for responses are provided in the data to indicate how much people trust AI-generated content for branded goods: "Completely trust," "Mostly trust," "Neutral," "Somewhat distrust," and "Do not trust at all."

The number of responses column shows that each trust level compared to the overall percentage of respondents. 4% of respondents said they "Completely trust" content produced by AI for branded goods. 62% of respondents, a sizable majority, said they "Mostly trust" content produced by AI. In terms of their level of trust in content produced by

AI, 28% of respondents are "Neutral." 6% of respondents said they "Somewhat distrust" content produced by AI.

Collectively, respondents had a favourable degree of trust (66%), with 4% "Completely trusting" and 62% "Mostly trusting" AI-generated content for branded products. This shows that the majority of respondents value material produced by AI. Many (28%) choose a "Neutral" approach, meaning they may not strongly trust or reject AI-generated content but are nonetheless receptive to it. Although none of the respondents stated, "Do not trust at all," a lower fraction (6%) "Somewhat distrusts" AI-generated content, indicating that open mistrust is uncommon among this demographic.

Table 11: Do you think AI will have more of an impact on future customer attitudes towards branded goods?

Impact of AI on future customer attitudes towards branded goods	Counts	Percentage
Strongly believe	19	19%
Somewhat believe	63	63%
Neutral	16	16%
Somewhat disbelieve	1	1%
Strongly disbelieve	1	1%

Chart 11: Impact of AI on future customer attitudes towards branded goods

The insight given refers to people's perceptions on how AI will affect consumers' views towards branded items in the future. The information offers five response choices that indicate how strongly people believe AI will affect how future consumers would perceive branded goods: Strongly, somewhat, neutrally, somewhat disbelieving, and strongly disbelieving are all acceptable statements of belief.

Each belief category's percentage of respondents, as compared to all respondents, is shown in the percentage column. 19% of respondents indicated to "Strongly believe" AI would have a big influence on how consumers feel about branded items in the future. 63% of respondents responded to "Somewhat believe" in AI's influence. According to 16% of respondents, they are "Neutral" about AI's effects. Almost no one (less than 1%) "somewhat disbelieves" in the effects of AI. A further minuscule 1 percent "Strongly disbelieves" in the influence of AI.

Following are a few ways AI is expected to affect consumer perceptions of branded goods:

- **Customization:** By delivering recommendations, offers, and information that are customised to each person's

requirements and interests, AI may be used to personalise the customer experience. With deeper consumer interactions and more enjoyable and engaging purchasing experiences, companies may benefit from this.

- **Automation:** AI may be used to automate processes like order fulfilment and customer service. This can increase the productivity and precision of these activities while allowing human workers to concentrate on more imaginative and strategic work.
- **Transparency:** AI may be used to provide customers greater information about how their data is being utilised in a transparent manner. This can support the development of consumer and brand confidence.
- **Innovation:** AI may be utilised to produce fresh concepts and ideas, which can assist businesses in creating cutting-edge goods and services.
- **Optimisation:** AI may be used to increase the effectiveness of some processes, like marketing and supply chain management. This can assist businesses in making cost savings and enhancing their bottom line.

Table 12: What possible negative effects of brand-product purchase decisions affected by AI do you see?

Purchase decision of branded products affected by AI	Counts	Percentage
Loss of genuine human interaction	41	41%
Over reliance on AI recommendations	50	50%
Privacy concerns	47	47%
Limited exposure to new options	18	18%

Chart 12: Purchase decision of branded products affected by AI

According to the figures, these are the main worries regarding how AI may affect consumer decisions to buy particular brands or products:

- **Loss of genuine human interaction:** 41% of individuals are worried that the loss of human connection in the shopping experience would be caused by AI-powered suggestions. They are concerned that they won't be able to speak with a customer support agent in depth or receive personalised advice from a salesperson.
- **Over reliance on AI recommendations:** 50% of those polled worry that they will rely too much on AI advice and lose the ability to make wise selections when making purchases. They are concerned that if they only follow

the AI's recommendations, they may be more inclined to purchase things that are inappropriate for them.

- **Privacy concerns:** 47% of respondents are worried about how AI-driven suggestions may affect their privacy. They are concerned that their personal information will be used to monitor their purchasing patterns and target them with ads.
- **Limited exposure to new options:** 18% of consumers worry that suggestions generated by AI may limit their exposure to fresh possibilities. They fear that instead of learning about fresh and interesting things, they will only be shown products that are identical to those they have already purchased.

In overall, the research reveals a number of drawbacks that people identify with AI's impact on their decisions to buy branded goods. These challenges include the decline of interpersonal communication, an over dependence on AI advice, privacy concerns, and a lack of exposure to novel possibilities. These worries highlight how complicated and varied the effects of AI on consumer behaviour and decision-making are.

XII. CONCLUSION

Our research corroborates that understanding customer buying habits is key to making the desired changes in online buying behaviour. AI tools appear to be powerful tools to achieve this goal, as they provide valuable data on various aspects that influence customer behavioural intentions. It also provides powerful tools to influence end-user behaviour by providing hands-on product recommendations, encouraging shopping, and customizing product offerings. It is also responsible for promoting other behaviours that increase the likelihood of sustainable online purchases. This is especially true when support frameworks such as purchase duration and reliance on social media are favourable to the marketer. Internally managed factors—machine learning, product recommendations, and purchase duration—had a significant impact on customer purchase intent.

The fact that a sizable majority of respondents claimed to be familiar with AI suggests that technology is well known and understood by consumers. This shows that AI-driven solutions have been widely adopted in many areas of customers' life. When purchasing, the vast majority of respondents claimed they preferred branded items than generic ones. This implies that recommendations created by AI have a considerable influence on customer decisions, especially when it comes to branded goods. Based on AI recommendations, the most important elements influencing consumers' decisions to purchase branded items were shown to be favourable ratings from other users, pertinent product information, and personalised suggestions. This underlines how crucial it is for AI-generated information to be trustworthy and relevant. AI will affect future consumer perceptions of branded goods. This shows that the potential impact of AI on consumer choices and behaviour has become widely acknowledged. Potential drawbacks of AI-influenced purchasing decisions include worries about over-reliance on AI recommendations, loss of true human connection, privacy issues, and restricted exposure to new possibilities. These worries highlight how intricate and subtle AI's influence on consumer decision-making is. Understanding and resolving these factors will be essential for businesses and regulators alike as AI continues to develop and integrate into the consumer market. This study advances preliminary understanding of the intricate interactions between consumer behaviour and AI in the case of branded goods purchases.

These results suggest that e-commerce companies should use these factors in an effort to increase customer awareness of the products they sell. Social media isn't a big predictor of your thought set, but it's still a great marketing channel that can help improve other aspects of your

business. This study has some serious limitations that may limit the applicability of our results.

Shopper are straightforwardly connected to Artificial insights and what it brings, they will need to know the affect it'll have upon them. With this data created through the frameworks, brands will create way better offering procedures to the customer's right when they have something and purchase it. Here we see at the effect of Manufactured insights on customer propensities and how it can manage the way shoppers purchase items and administrations from the showcase for the days to come.

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